

GENDER DISPARITIES AND MATHEMATICS PERFORMANCE OF JUNIOR HIGH SCHOOL STUDENTS

Guadosa U. Villalon¹, Joel T. Ubat², Sherwin A. Jakosalem², Jake Faburada²

¹ *Caidiocan Elementary School, District of Valencia, Negros Oriental, Philippines*

² *Mathematics Department, Negros Oriental State University- Guihulngan, Philippines*

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ABSTRACT

This study seeks to explore gender disparities in mathematics and how it affects the academic performance of male, and female students in the mathematics subject. The researchers used an adapted questionnaire to gather the data from 133 grade 10 respondents coming from the Guihulngan National High School–Hilaitan which 60 of them are male and 73 of them are female. Analyses of the responses lead to notable results. It shows that male respondents have higher self-efficacy than females having a weighted mean of 3.47 than the 3.35 of females. Though the result reveals that they have the same level of attitudes towards learning mathematics, a discrepancy is still seen in their mathematics performance which is derived from their third-quarter mathematics examination scores. There were a larger number of male respondents who got high scores labeled as having an outstanding performance while female respondents outnumbered males in the group of students having poor performance in their mathematics quarterly examination. The following results lead to a conclusion that males have a better performance than females in mathematics upon comparing their weighted mean, therefore indicating that gender disparities influence the mathematics performance of the grade 10 students in GNHS–Hilaitan.

Keywords: *Gender Disparity, Mathematics Self-Efficacy, Self-Confidence in Mathematics, Value for Mathematics, Mathematics Enjoyment, Motivation Towards Learning Mathematics*

INTRODUCTION

Mathematics is about problem-solving and critical thinking. It teaches us to analyze data, identify patterns, and develop creative solutions to complex problems (Sam, 2024). It also plays a crucial role in the modern world as it encompasses a wide scope of disciplines that help us understand the world around us such as medicine, engineering, economics, etc. With the help of mathematics, the world can devise solutions for its existing problems. However, if the general world has its problems, mathematics has also its concerns. Gender disparity in mathematics is the difference between males and females in their performance in this subject. Males and females behave differently and project different attitudes toward their learning in mathematics. They do not also share the same level of confidence regarding this subject because some would still say that it is hard for them to learn and understand math while other students feel the opposite. For instance, male students are more confident than females in the correctness of their math solutions (McMurran et al, 2023).

The disparities in mathematics performance among students are not new to this world. There have been studies worldwide that focus on this issue but remains debatable whether gender differences in mathematics performance exist and what the sources of these differences are. However, researchers across the globe continuously conduct their studies to prove that this issue exists. According to the December 2023 news report of ANSA English, an English-language service for Italy's leading news wire, the country has the largest difference between girls and boys in attainment in mathematics among the 81 countries taking part in the OECD's Programme for International Student Assessment (PISA) study, based on the latest edition of the report. It is revealed in this study that 15-year-old Italian boys outperformed female students of the same age by 21 points in this subject. In Western China, gender differences in mathematics also occur across different mathematical abilities. Female students' high school mathematics academic performance is significantly better than that of male students as male students' scores in basic skills, mathematical operations, and data analysis are significantly lower than that of female students. Female students also perform better than males in the knowledge modules of sets, complex numbers, plane vectors, statistics, trigonometry, analytic geometry, and functions (Jiang, 2021).

In the Philippines, the gender gap favoring boys in mathematics at early grades gradually disappears, and girls show better performance than boys according to UNESCO's Global Education Monitoring Report 2022. PISA 2022 data also revealed that Filipino male students have a larger share of low performers in mathematics having 86% than the 82% of females.

In future career choices, students also have different perceptions in mathematics-related fields as the 2021 report by the World Bank Group (WBG) shows that there is still a notable and wider gender gap in the participation of women and girls (relative to men and boys) in the Science, Technology, Engineering, and Mathematics (STEM)-related education and employment. The data from the National Science Foundation (NSF) also revealed that globally, only 7% of women choose to study construction, engineering, and manufacturing compared to 22% of men.

These data show that gender disparities in mathematics performance among students still exist. The evidence presented by the researchers of this study proves that there is a need for this study to be conducted especially in the Guihulngan National High School-Hilaitan.

Research Questions

This study explores gender disparities in the mathematics performance of Grade 10 students in Guihulngan National High School-Hilaitan.

Specifically, this study seeks to answer the following queries:

1. What is the profile of the respondents in terms of:
 - 1.1. Age;
 - 1.2. Gender?
2. What is the mathematics performance of the respondents in terms of their third quarter examination score?
3. What is the level of gender disparity existing in the mathematics performance of the students in terms of:
 - 3.1. Mathematics Self-Efficacy;
 - 3.2. Attitudes towards learning mathematics based on their:
 - 3.2.1. Self-Confidence;
 - 3.2.2. Value;
 - 3.2.3. Enjoyment; and
 - 3.2.4. Motivation?
4. Is there a significant relationship between the level of gender disparity and mathematics performance of the students?

METHODOLOGY

Design

The method that was used in conducting this study was the survey methodology through a survey questionnaire. The researchers used an adopted questionnaire to obtain the needed data or information about the gender disparity in the mathematics performance of GNHS-Hilaitan Grade 10 students. The data gathered from the researchers are expected to form the core data of the study.

Environment

This study was conducted at Guihulngan National High School–Hilaitan, a secondary school in Brgy. Hilaitan, Guihulngan City, Negros Oriental under the Division of Guihulngan City, Central Visayas Region. The researchers selected the research site because one of them is an alumnus of the said school and had observed that there have

been gender disparities existing in the students in terms of their self-efficacy and attitudes towards learning mathematics which somehow affected their performance in the course.

The researchers collected data about gender differences in mathematics self-efficacy and attitudes toward learning mathematics for them, as future mathematics educators, to devise solutions to alleviating gender disparities in terms of the attitudes of the students and developing their mathematics self-efficacy.

Respondents

The respondents of this study were grade 10 students in the Guihulngan National High School–Hilaitan, S.Y. 2023-2024. There was a total of 201 grade 10 students in GNHS-Hilaitan.

Instrument

The research instrument used in this study has 2 parts, the Mathematics Self-Efficacy and the Attitudes towards Learning Mathematics.

In the first part, the researchers based and adapted the questionnaire on the Mathematics Self-Efficacy and Anxiety Questionnaire (MSEAQ) by May (2009) to determine the students' levels of anxiety and self-efficacy in mathematics. The researchers only adopted the Self-Efficacy tool comprising 14 items to determine the student's level of self-efficacy because it is the only one needed.

Meanwhile, the second part was an adapted survey questionnaire developed by Tapia and Marsh (2004) in English, "The Attitudes Toward Mathematics Inventory." The research questionnaire has four subscales. These include self-confidence, value, enjoyment, and motivation. These four subscales were narrowed down according to the elements of Malik (2018) definition of attitudes toward mathematics. Self-confidence is defined as a belief that one is good or bad at mathematics, value is a belief that mathematics is useful or useless, enjoyment is an aggregated measure of liking or disliking mathematics, and motivation is a tendency to engage in or avoid mathematical activities.

The questionnaire was used in the previous study by Laranang & Bondoc (2020) entitled "Attitudes and Self-Efficacy of the Students Toward Mathematics". Thus, this instrument is valid and reliable. The components in the questionnaire also coincide with this study. Therefore, the questionnaire used by Laranang and Bondoc (2020) is the appropriate instrument to meet the study's objectives.

Data Gathering Procedure

In gathering the data, the researcher began by seeking approval from the school head of the school under investigation, GNHS-Hilaitan. Through a formal letter, the researcher will seek consent to proceed with distributing questionnaires to the selected respondents. Once the data collection phase is completed, the researcher will diligently organize, count, and interpret the statistical findings. To ensure accuracy and precision, the researcher

will work closely with a skilled statistician, who will provide valuable expertise in analyzing the collected data.

Treatment of Data

The researcher used the frequency count and percentage to determine the profile of the student's age and gender. To determine the level of gender disparity existing in the mathematics performance of the students in terms of mathematics self-efficacy and attitude toward learning mathematics, a weighted mean is used. The researcher also used the Pearson Product Moment Correlation to determine the significant relationship between gender disparity and the mathematics performance of the students.

RESULTS AND DISCUSSION

1. Demographic profile of the Respondents

Table 1.1. Descriptive statistics of the demographic profile of the respondents (n= 133)

	Frequency	Percentage
Age		
14	61	46
15	49	37
16	14	11
17	5	4
18	2	2
19	2	2
GENDER		
Male	60	45
Female	73	55

Table 1.1 shows that there were six (6) different classifications of age who participated in the survey: 14 years old, 15 years old, 16 years old, 17 years old, 18 years old, and 19 years old. There were 61 respondents aged 14 years old (46% of the total number of respondents), 49 of the total sample size were 15 years old (37%), there were also 14 respondents aged 16 years old (11%), five (5) were 17 years old (4%), (2) were 18 years old (2%), and two (2) were 19 years old (2%). Therefore, there were 133 grade 10 students who took part in the survey. It appears that **14-year-old students have the highest frequency** of 61. This tells that the majority of the respondents that are in 10th grade are aged 14 years old. Meanwhile **18 years old and 19 years old tallied the lowest frequency** of 2. This implies that only a few grade 10 students are 18 and 19-year-olds. It also shows that among the 133 respondents who participated in this study and answered the questionnaire, 60 of them (45% of the sample size) were male, while there were 73 respondents (55%) who labeled themselves as female.

1. Respondent's Mathematics Performance in the Third Quarter

Table 2. The frequency distribution of the respondents' mathematics performance.

Respondents	Below 36	36-37	38-39	40-42	43-48	Total
Male	33	8	8	2	9	60
Female	58	7	4	4	0	73
Total						133

Table 2 shows the frequency distribution of the respondent's examination scores in mathematics during their third quarter examination. The data reveals that there are more female respondents who got scores below 36 than males. It is also evident that there are 9 male respondents who got a score of 43-48 while female respondents recorded none. This implies that despite being outnumbered, males have a better performance in mathematics than females.

2. LEVEL OF GENDER DISPARITY EXISTING IN THE MATHEMATICS PERFORMANCE OF THE STUDENTS

Table 3.1. The Mathematics Self-Efficacy of the Male and Female Respondents.

	Male		Female	
	Weighted Mean	Verbal Interpretation	Weighted Mean	Verbal Interpretation
I feel confident enough to ask questions in my mathematics class.	3.37	Moderately High	3.48	High
I believe I can do well in a mathematics class.	3.50	High	3.38	Moderately High
I believe I can complete all the assignments in a mathematics subject.	3.42	High	3.64	High
I believe I am the kind of person who is good at mathematics.	3.33	Moderately High	3.00	Moderately High
I believe I will be able to use mathematics in the future when needed.	3.65	High	3.67	High
I believe I can understand the content of a mathematics subject.	3.48	High	3.38	Moderately High
I believe I can get an "A" when I am in mathematics subject.	3.55	High	3.15	Moderately High
I believe I can learn well in a mathematics subject.	3.58	High	3.53	High
I believe I can learn well in mathematics subject.	3.67	High	3.63	High

I believe I am the type of person who can do mathematics.	3.40	Moderately High	3.25	Moderately High
I feel that I will be able to do well in future mathematics subjects.	3.35	Moderately High	3.32	Moderately High
I believe I can do mathematics in a mathematics subject.	3.55	High	3.25	Moderately High
I believe I can think like a mathematician.	3.20	Moderately High	2.90	Moderately High
I feel confident when using mathematics outside of school.	3.50	High	3.29	Moderately High
Grand Weighted Mean	3.47	High	3.35	Moderately High

Table 3.1 presents the male and female respondents' level of self-efficacy in Mathematics. As shown in the table, the grand weighted mean for males was 3.47, verbally interpreted as high. This means that the male respondents have a high level of self-efficacy in mathematics. This implies that most of the respondents have high self-beliefs towards mathematics because they believe that they can do well in a mathematics class. They also believe that they can understand the content of a mathematics subject. Furthermore, most of the male respondents feel confident when using mathematics outside the school. This indicates that male respondents believe that they have high mathematical ability and can perform well in mathematics even outside the classroom. While, the grand weighted mean for females was 3.35, verbally interpreted as moderate. This means that the female respondents have a moderate level of self-efficacy in mathematics. This implies that most of the female respondents have an average level of self-belief in mathematics. They believe that they are mediocre in terms of their performance in mathematics class. Moreover, the majority of them moderately feel that they will be able to do well in future mathematics subjects. This indicates that the self-efficacy of female respondents towards mathematics is not at a high level but is not also at a low level, it suggests that they are at an average level when it comes to learning and applying mathematics on their own.

Figure 1 below shows the comparison of respondents' mathematics self-efficacy. It shows that male respondents have higher self-efficacy having a weighted mean of 3.47 than of the female's 3.35. This indicates that boys' self-belief in solving mathematics problems and overcoming difficulties in doing so is higher than girls. It certifies the findings of Zander, et al. (2020) that girls have much lower mathematics self-efficacy than boys, a likely contributor to the underrepresentation of women in STEM.

Figure 1. Respondents' Mathematics Self-Efficacy.

3.2. ATTITUDE TOWARDS LEARNING MATHEMATICS

Table 3.2.1. The Self-Confidence in Mathematics of Male and Female respondents.

	Weighted Mean	Verbal Interpretation	Weighted Mean	Verbal Interpretation
Mathematics does not scare me at all.	3.22	Moderately High	3.03	Moderately High
I have a lot of self-confidence when it comes to mathematics.	3.33	Moderately High	3.07	Moderately High
I can do mathematics experiments without too much difficulty.	3.13	Moderately High	2.99	Moderately High
I expect to do well in any mathematics class I take.	3.45	High	3.26	Moderately High
I am always confused about my mathematics class.	3.38	Moderately High	3.21	Moderately High
I feel sense of insecurity when attempting mathematics.	3.45	High	3.04	Moderately High
I learn mathematics quickly.	3.33	Moderately High	3.32	Moderately High
I am confident that I could learn advanced mathematics.	3.33	Moderately High	3.19	Moderately High

I have usually enjoyed studying mathematics at school.	3.60	High	3.42	High
Mathematics is dull and boring.	2.77	Moderately High	2.38	Low
I like to do new experiments in mathematics.	3.48	High	3.38	Moderately High
I would prefer to experiment with mathematics than to write essay.	3.30	Moderately High	3.12	Moderately High
I would like to avoid using mathematics in college.	3.07	Moderately High	3.04	Moderately High
I like mathematics.	3.65	High	3.62	High
I believe I am good at mathematics experiments.	3.60	High	3.11	Moderately High
Grand Weighted Mean	3.34	Moderately High	3.15	Moderately High

Table 3.2.1 presents the male and female respondents' level of self-confidence in mathematics. It shows that the male respondents have a moderate level of self-confidence in mathematics, which can be observed in the general weighted mean of 3.34. This implies that male respondents felt not too much difficulty but not too much ease as well when it comes to mathematics. They are not quick to learn mathematics, but they are not also slow in mathematics lessons. They also have a moderate level of confidence in experimenting with mathematics than in writing essays. However, most of them believe that they are good at mathematics experiments and do like the subject. This indicates that even if the male respondents like mathematics and mathematics experiments rather than essays, they still do not have a high level of confidence in mathematics. However, that does not mean that male respondents have low self-esteem in mathematics, they are just average. While the female respondents' level of self-confidence in mathematics was 3.15 as the general weighted mean. This implies that female respondents felt moderately confident in mathematics. For instance, their self-esteem is not that high but also not low when asked whether mathematics scares them or not. Despite having a majority of their level labeled as moderate, they still like mathematics and enjoy studying mathematics at school. They do not agree with the notion that mathematics is dull as most of them oppose the statement. This disproves the findings of De La Rosa (2020) More male students favor math and have more confidence in the subject matter than their female counterparts, according to a survey by the Society for Industrial Applied Mathematics.

Table 3.2.2. The Value of Mathematics of Male Respondents.

	Weighted Mean	Verbal Interpretation	Weighted Mean	Verbal Interpretation
Mathematics is very worthwhile and necessary subject.	3.27	Moderately High	3.40	Moderately High
I want to develop my mathematics skills.	3.57	High	3.79	High

I get a great deal of satisfaction out of mathematics experiments.	3.35	Moderately High	3.29	Moderately High
Mathematics help develop the mind and teaches a person to think.	3.43	High	3.63	High
Mathematics is vital in every life.	3.37	Moderately High	3.47	High
Mathematics is one of the most important subjects for people to study.	3.37	Moderately High	3.66	High
High school mathematics subjects would be beneficial no matter what I decide to study.	3.42	High	3.44	High
I can think of many ways that I use mathematics outside of school.	3.43	High	3.37	Moderately High
Mathematics is one of my most dreaded/feared subjects.	3.35	Moderately High	3.11	Moderately High
My mind goes blank, and I am unable to think clearly when studying mathematics.	3.30	Moderately High	2.97	Moderately High
Grand Weighted Mean	3.39	Moderately High	3.41	High

Table 3.2.2 shows that the male respondents have moderately high values towards mathematics, as shown in the grand weighted mean of 3.39. This means that the male respondents have an average value in learning math. This further implies that male respondents still view mathematics as a valuable subject in life. They even agree with the statement that “mathematics helps develop the mind and teaches a person to think”, resulting in a weighted mean of 3.43, labeled as ‘high’. While, the female respondents have a high value for mathematics, having a weighted mean of 3.41, labeled as “high”. This means that female respondents have a high value in learning mathematics. They even got the highest weighted mean of 3.79 when it talks about developing their mathematics skills. This simply suggests that honing their abilities in mathematics could greatly help them in future endeavors as they also produced a weighted mean of 3.66 in the statement “Mathematics is one of the most important subjects for people to study.”

This result shows that girls tend to value mathematics more than boys, a contradiction to the findings of Ghasemi and Burley (2019) that boys revealed value mathematics more than girls.

Table 3.2.3. The Enjoyment of Mathematics of Male Respondents.

	Weighted Mean	Verbal Interpretation	Weighted Mean	Verbal Interpretation
I am happier in a mathematics class than in any other class.	3.53	High	3.14	Moderately High
Mathematics is a fascinating subject.	3.27	Moderately High	3.18	Moderately High
I am willing to take more than the required amount of mathematics.	3.60	High	3.21	Moderately High
I plan to take as much mathematics as I can during my education.	3.57	High	3.34	Moderately High
The challenge of mathematics appeals to me.	3.64	High	3.38	Moderately High
I think studying advanced in mathematics is useful.	3.43	High	3.68	High
I believe that studying mathematics helps me with problem-solving in other areas.	3.60	High	3.55	High
I am comfortable expressing my ideas on how to look for solutions to a problematic mathematics experiment.	3.35	Moderately High	3.32	Moderately High
I am comfortable answering questions in mathematics class.	3.45	High	3.27	Moderately High
A strong mathematics background could help me in my professional life.	3.57	High	3.51	High
Grand Weighted Mean	3.50	High	3.36	Moderately High

The table above shows that male respondents have a high level of enjoyment in mathematics, having a grand weighted mean of 3.50. Although having a moderately high level of comfort in answering questions in mathematics class with a weighted mean of 3.45, they still find themselves happier in mathematics class than in any other class, tallying a weighted mean of 3.53 which indicates a high level. This shows that male participants of this study find mathematics fun and enjoyable to study. While, the female respondents have a moderately high level of enjoyment in mathematics, having a grand weighted mean of 3.36. Female respondents show a moderately high level of enjoyment when they are in a mathematics class. Although they think that studying advanced mathematics is useful and believe that it helps them with problem-solving in other areas, they are still not comfortable expressing ideas on how to look for solutions to a problematic mathematics experiment and answering questions in mathematics class. This indicates that female respondents somehow learn mathematics.

The result shows that boys enjoy mathematics more than girls. This concurs with the study by Davis (2020) that boys are more confident in their abilities in math and science and enjoy the subjects more than girls.

Table 3.2.4. The Motivation Towards Mathematics of Male Respondents.

	Weighted Mean	Verbal Interpretation	Weighted Mean	Verbal Interpretation
Studying mathematics makes me feel nervous.	3.17	Moderately High	3.08	Moderately High
Mathematics makes me feel uncomfortable.	3.03	Moderately High	2.81	Moderately High
I am always under a terrible strain in a mathematics class.	3.10	Moderately High	2.97	Moderately High
When I hear the word mathematics, I have a feeling of dislike.	2.95	Moderately High	2.78	Moderately High
It makes me nervous to even think about having to do a mathematics experiment.	3.18	Moderately High	3.07	Moderately High
Grand Weighted Mean	3.09	Moderately High	2.94	Moderately High

As shown in Table 3.2.4 above, male respondents have a moderately high level of motivation towards mathematics, having a grand weighted mean of 3.09. This implies that they have an average level of motivation in learning mathematics. While, the female respondents have a moderately high level of motivation when it comes to mathematics, with a grand weighted mean of 2.94. This data suggests that female respondents have a moderate level of motivation in studying and learning mathematics.

Table 3.2.5. presents the summary of the level of attitude of the male and female respondents towards learning mathematics.

	Grand Weighted Mean	Verbal Interpretation	Grand Weighted Mean	Verbal Interpretation
Self-Confidence in Mathematics	3.34	Moderately High	3.15	Moderately High
Value for Mathematics	3.39	Moderately High	3.41	High
Enjoyment of Mathematics	3.50	High	3.36	Moderately High
Motivation towards Mathematics	3.09	Moderately High	2.94	Moderately High

Overall Weighted Mean	3.33	Moderately High	3.21	Moderately High
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Table 3.2.5 presents the consolidated grand weighted mean of male respondents in their attitude towards learning mathematics, gauged through a thorough examination of the levels of their self-confidence, value, enjoyment, and motivation towards mathematics. The level of attitude towards learning mathematics is identified by getting the average of the four categories of attitudes which resulted in an overall weighted mean of 3.33, a moderately high level of attitude towards learning mathematics. This indicates that the male participants of this study project had a moderate attitude towards learning mathematics. The consolidated grand weighted mean of female respondents in their attitude towards learning mathematics, as determined by a thorough examination of the levels of their self-confidence, value, enjoyment, and motivation towards mathematics. The overall weighted mean of the female respondents, which is 3.21 at a moderately high level, indicates that they have an average level of attitude when they are studying and learning mathematics.

3. CORRELATION BETWEEN THE LEVEL OF GENDER DISPARITY AND LEARNER'S MATHEMATICS PERFORMANCE.

Table 4.1 presents the correlation between mathematics self-efficacy and the attitude of the male respondents towards learning mathematics and their mathematics performance.

Mathematics Self-Efficacy	Computed r	Tabular value	Degree of Relationship	Decision	Interpretation
Male	0.641	0.087	High	Reject H_o	Significant
Female	0.453	0.087	Moderate	Reject H_o	Significant

Table 4.1 reveals that there is a difference between the male and female respondents in terms of their mathematics self-efficacy. The computed r of the male respondents is 0.641. This leads to the conclusion that there is a high level of correlation between the males' mathematics self-efficacy and their mathematics performance. Since the computed r is greater than the tabular value of 0.087, this implies that the null hypothesis is rejected and therefore, there is a significant relationship between the males' mathematics self-efficacy and their mathematics performance.

On the other hand, female respondents have a computed r of 0.453. It indicates a moderate level of self-confidence among female respondents. Since the computed r is greater than the tabular value of 0.087, this leads to the rejection of the null hypothesis and therefore, it marks a significant relationship between the females' mathematics self-efficacy and their mathematics performance.

Table 4.2.1 presents the correlation between the attitude of the male respondents towards learning mathematics and their mathematics performance.

Attitude Towards Learning Mathematics	Computed r	Tabular value	Degree of Relationship	Decision	Interpretation
Self-confidence	0.591	0.087	Moderate	Reject H_o	Significant
Value	0.481	0.087	Moderate	Reject H_o	Significant
Enjoyment	0.554	0.087	Moderate	Reject H_o	Significant
Motivation	0.211	0.087	Low	Reject H_o	Significant
Overall	0.459	0.087	Moderate	Reject H_o	Significant

Table 4.2.1 shows the correlation between the attitude of male respondents towards learning mathematics specifically their self-confidence, value of mathematics, enjoyment, and motivation towards mathematics, and their mathematics performance. After applying the Pearson's product-moment correlation coefficient on each sub-variable, the following data were obtained. The result shows that male respondents' self-confidence in mathematics has a computed r of 0.591 which is greater than the tabular value of 0.087. This indicates that the relationship between the male respondents' self-confidence has a moderate correlation to their mathematics performance. This leads to the rejection of the null hypothesis; therefore, the relationship is significant.

Male respondents' value for mathematics has a computed r of 0.481 which is also greater than the tabular value of 0.087. This indicates that the relationship between the male respondents' value of mathematics has a moderate correlation to their mathematics performance. This leads to the rejection of the null hypothesis; therefore, the relationship is significant. Male respondents' enjoyment of mathematics has a computed r of 0.554 which is also greater than the tabular value of 0.087. This indicates that the relationship between the male respondents' enjoyment of mathematics has a moderate correlation to their mathematics performance. This leads to the rejection of the null hypothesis; therefore, the relationship is significant.

Male respondents' motivation towards mathematics has a computed r of 0.211 which is also greater than the tabular value of 0.087. This indicates that the relationship between the male respondents' value of mathematics has a low correlation to their mathematics performance. This leads to the rejection of the null hypothesis; therefore, the relationship is significant.

Based on the data obtained, this indicates that the overall computed r of the sub-variables is 0.459. This means that the computed r of the male respondents' attitude towards learning mathematics is still greater than the tabular value of 0.087. This implies that there is a moderate correlation between the male respondents' attitudes towards learning

mathematics and their mathematics performance. This leads to the rejection of the null hypothesis; therefore, the relationship is significant.

Table 4.2.2 presents the correlation between the attitude of the female respondents towards learning mathematics and their mathematics performance.

Attitude Towards Learning Mathematics	Computed r	Tabular value	Degree of Relationship	Decision	Interpretation
Self-confidence	0.609	0.087	High	Reject H_o	Significant
Value	0.465	0.087	Moderate	Reject H_o	Significant
Enjoyment	0.471	0.087	Moderate	Reject H_o	Significant
Motivation	0.044	0.087	Negligible	Fail to Reject H_o	Not Significant
Overall	0.397	0.087	Low	Reject H_o	Significant

Table 4.2.2 shows the correlation between the attitude of female respondents towards learning mathematics specifically their self-confidence, value of mathematics, enjoyment, and motivation towards mathematics, and their mathematics performance. Pearson's product-moment correlation coefficient was still applied to each sub-variable to obtain the following data.

The table reveals that the self-confidence of female respondents in mathematics has a high correlation to their exam score, having a computed r of 0.609 which is greater than the tabular value of 0.087. This leads to the rejection of the null hypothesis, indicating that there is a significant relationship between the female respondents' self-confidence in mathematics and their mathematics performance. On the value for mathematics, female respondents; computed r is at 0.465 which is still greater than the tabular value of 0.087. This implies that there is a moderate correlation between their value for mathematics and their mathematics performance. Hence, the null hypothesis is rejected indicating a significant relationship between the two variables. On the female respondents' responses to the 'enjoyment of mathematics' questions, it tallied a computed r of 0.471 which is also greater than the tabular value of 0.087. This still indicates a moderate correlation between their enjoyment of mathematics and their mathematics performance. The researchers rejected the null hypothesis and concluded the relationship as significant. It further reveals the female respondents' computed r on the motivation towards mathematics at 0.044, a value that is less than the tabular value of 0.087, a negligible correlation. This implies that the null hypothesis will not be rejected, and it will be marked as not significant.

Despite having a negligible correlation on the motivation towards mathematics, the overall computed r of the female respondents in the attitude towards learning mathematics is still at 0.397, greater than the tabular value of 0.087. However, the correlation between the two variables is low. There is somehow a correlation, but it is not strong. The null hypothesis is still rejected which indicates a significant relationship between the attitudes

of the female respondents towards learning mathematics and their mathematics performance.

Table 4.2.3 presents the correlation between mathematics self-efficacy and the attitude of the male respondents towards learning mathematics and their mathematics performance.

Factors Affecting Gender Disparity	Computed r	Tabular value	Degree of Relationship	Decision	Interpretation
Self-Efficacy	0.641	0.087	High	Reject H_o	Significant
Attitude	0.459	0.087	Moderate	Reject H_o	Significant
Overall	0.550	0.087	Moderate	Reject H_o	Significant

Table 4.2.3 presents the correlation between the male's mathematics self-efficacy and attitude towards learning mathematics. Based on the computed r of 0.55, there is a moderate correlation between the males' disparity in mathematics self-efficacy and attitude towards learning mathematics and their mathematics performance. Since the computed r is greater than the tabular value of 0.087, it leads to the rejection of the null hypothesis. Therefore, there is a significant relationship between their mathematics self-efficacy and attitude towards learning mathematics, and their mathematics performance. It implies that these factors can affect their mathematics performance but on a moderate level only.

Table 4.2.4 presents the correlation between mathematics self-efficacy and the attitude of the female respondents towards learning mathematics and their mathematics performance.

Factors Affecting Gender Disparity	Computed r	Tabular value	Degree of Relationship	Decision	Interpretation
Self-Efficacy	0.453	0.087	Moderate	Reject H_o	Significant
Attitude	0.397	0.087	Low	Reject H_o	Significant
Overall	0.425	0.087	Moderate	Reject H_o	Significant

Table 4.2.5 reveals that the computed r of the self-efficacy and attitude of female respondents towards mathematics is 0.425, indicating a moderate correlation. Since the computed r is greater than the tabular value of 0.087 (computed r (0.425) > tabular value (0.087)), the null hypothesis is rejected. Therefore, there is a significant relationship between the factors affecting gender disparity and the females' mathematics performance. This implies that these factors can have an effect on their mathematics performance but at a moderate level.

Table 4.2.6 presents the gender disparity of the respondents in terms of their mathematics self-efficacy and their attitude towards learning mathematics, and its correlation to their mathematics performance.

Gender Disparity	Computed r	Tabular value	Degree of Relationship	Decision	Interpretation
Male	0.550	0.087	Moderate	Reject H_o	Significant
Female	0.425	0.087	Moderate	Reject H_o	Significant

Table 4.2.6 discusses the gender disparity of the respondents in terms of their mathematics self-efficacy and their attitude towards learning mathematics, and its correlation to their mathematics performance. The table reveals that both males and females have a moderate correlation to their mathematics performance. However, there is a small difference in their computed r as male has a higher value than females. This implies that boys perform better than girls in mathematics by a slight distinction.

Conclusions

Based on our analysis of the data, the research findings reveal significant gender differences in mathematics self-efficacy and attitudes. Males exhibit higher levels of mathematics self-efficacy, with a grand weighted mean of 3.47, surpassing the corresponding mean of 3.35 for females. When exploring gender disparities in attitudes towards mathematics, males demonstrate a superior level of self-confidence in math, as indicated by a general weighted mean of 3.34, compared to females who achieved a slightly lower mean of 3.15. Additionally, the perception of the value of mathematics differs between genders, with females showing a higher level of value, reflected which has a general weighted mean of 3.41, while males' weighted mean is slightly lower at 3.39. Furthermore, the enjoyment of mathematics appears to vary between males and females, with males getting a higher level of enjoyment with a general weighted mean of 3.50, in contrast to females who got 3.36. In terms of motivation towards mathematics, males also exhibit a higher level of motivation, with a general weighted mean of 3.09, compared to females with a mean of 2.94. The results reveal that both male and female students exhibit a moderate correlation with their mathematics performance. However, a slight distinction emerges in their computed correlation coefficient (r), with males achieving a higher value of 0.550 compared to females with a value of 0.425. This difference implies that boys demonstrate a slightly better performance in mathematics than girls.

Recommendations

With all the foregoing analysis, interpretation, and conclusions of this study, the researchers have come up with the following recommendations for possible courses of action. As for the students, they are encouraged to monitor their academic performance in mathematics as a majority of them obtained low scores in their mathematics quarterly

examination, and above half of the total respondents were performing poorly. Female students, need to improve their self-confidence and have more trust in themselves when engaging in mathematics subject. In this way, they can improve their enjoyment and motivation, fostering a better academic outcome. For male students, enjoyment alone does not keep them at a good performance. The researchers also encourage them to monitor their learning and develop confidence in dealing with mathematics. They can use their enjoyment of mathematics to discover more concepts in mathematics and appreciate its essence in everyday life.

This study will also help the teachers assess their teaching approaches and devise new strategies to enhance the deficiencies of their students in terms of their performance in mathematics. It is highly advised that they look for other approaches that engage students in the subject and develop an appreciation of its concepts. This study will also serve as an opportunity for future researchers as a valuable reference point, offering insights and findings that can contribute to further exploration and development in the field of education. Future researchers can look for other factors affecting gender disparities and their mathematics performance. They can widen the scope of the study to explore more factors. These recommendations aim to enhance student engagement, and academic outcomes, and support continuous research efforts in education.

Compliance with Ethical Standards

In gathering the essential data for this study, the researchers wrote a letter addressed to the principal of Guihulngan National High School-Hilaitan, signed by the research adviser, to ask for consent to surveying their grade 10 students. After the principal receives the letter, the date is then scheduled for the conduct of the survey. The researchers ensured that the information obtained during the survey shall remain confidential, as stated in its cover letter. The questionnaire only contains the essential information for the study such as the respondent's gender and their test score in mathematics, and these shall only be used for the completion of this study

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